

DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL CULTURE OF STUDENTS OF ACADEMIC LYCEUM, SECONDARY SPECIAL AND PROFESSIONAL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS ON THE BASIS OF A COMPETENT APPROACH

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Abstract. This article is aimed at developing the professional culture of students of academic lyceums, secondary special and vocational education institutions on the basis of a competent approach.

Keywords: education, science, knowledge, technology, competence, skill, professional culture, engineering, theoretical, practical, qualification, quality, research.

РАЗВИТИЕ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ СТУДЕНТОВ АКАДЕМИЧЕСКОГО ЛИЦЕЯ, СРЕДНИХ СПЕЦИАЛЬНЫХ И ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНЫХ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ УЧРЕЖДЕНИЙ НА ОСНОВЕ КОМПЕТЕНТНОГО ПОДХОДА

Аннотация. Данная статья направлена на развитие профессиональной культуры учащихся академических лицеев, учреждений среднего специального и профессионального образования на основе компетентностного подхода.

Ключевые слова: образование, наука, знания, технология, компетентность, мастерство, профессиональная культура, инженерия, теоретическая, практическая, квалификация, качество, исследование.

INTRODUCTION

The Resolutions and Decrees adopted by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in recent years [1-5] prove that the issue of improving the quality of education in secondary, special, academic lyceums and vocational education institutions is being addressed at the state policy level.

In our country, the main goal and driving force of the reforms are to bring up people who are fully developed, have a highly professional culture, are creative, socially active, and feel responsible to society, the state and the family. So far, the improvement of the academic lyceum, secondary special and vocational education system on the basis of advanced foreign experience, and training of qualified and competitive personnel for the labor market through the introduction of primary, secondary and secondary special vocational education has been identified as a priority. To address this topical issue, the development of innovative technologies for the organization of vocational education in educational institutions, especially in academic lyceums, secondary special and vocational education, requires pedagogical research in these areas. Given the urgency of this problem, it is necessary to study the problem of developing the professional culture of students of academic lyceums, and secondary special and vocational education institutions on the basis of a competent approach from a scientific and pedagogical point of view.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

The globalization of education and the introduction of modern pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process lead to an increase in the quality of education in educational institutions. It is well known that any technology is based on principles

that shape the new content of education. The active subjects of the modern educational process are teachers and students, whose joint activities allow them to deepen their theoretical and practical knowledge on a particular topic [6].

Achieving quality and efficiency in the teaching of physics in educational institutions, and, consequently, in the training of competitive modern teaching staff and engineers, many problems can not be achieved without solving many problems [7]. Academic lyceums and secondary special and vocational education institutions play a key role in directing students to a particular profession, including irrigation and land reclamation, and agricultural engineering. "Competence" is the ability of graduates to improve their personal qualities and knowledge, skills and abilities in a particular game, and to use them in the effective performance of professional functions based on work experience.

In our opinion, "competence" means the ability to independently apply the knowledge and skills acquired by students in personal, professional and social activities.

In the process of physical education in academic lyceums, secondary special and vocational education institutions, it is necessary to be aware of the basic concepts and their content in the study of existing problems in the implementation of competence requirements and ways to overcome them and the development of a professional culture of students based on a competency approach.

RESEARCH RESULTS

In the XXI century, one of the main directions of modernization of the content of education in the developed countries of the world is the introduction of a competency-based approach to education. Education based on a competency-based approach is education aimed at developing students' ability to apply the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities in practice in their personal, professional and social activities [8].

Development of the professional culture of students of the educational institutions based on the competency approach is a pedagogical process aimed at cultivating the qualities of professional competence in students, ensuring their high intellectual, psychological, physiological, spiritual and moral maturity based on the priority of positive attitude to professional activity. The effective organization of this process depends on its organizational, methodological and practical aspects.

Education based on a competency-based approach develops students' independence, active citizenship, initiative, rational use of media resources and information and communication technologies in their work, conscious career choice, healthy competition and intercultural skills [6].

In particular, the pedagogical description of the concepts of "competence", "level of competence", "competence approach", "professional culture" and "development" correctly organizes scientific and pedagogical activities aimed at solving the problem and, most importantly, successful pilot work. provides an opportunity to be effective in organizing research.

The word competence is derived from the Latin words "competo", and "competentia", which means to achieve, conform and deserve. The essence of this term is characterized by such concepts as success, efficiency, and achievement [8].

Professional competence is a quality that characterizes and evaluates a person's special activity in the social labour system. They are described as: a deep understanding of the nature of

the tasks and problems to be performed, a good knowledge of the experience in the field, a good mastery of it, a choice of appropriate tools and methods of action in a specific place and time, a sense of responsibility for the result.

The concepts of “competence” and “professional competence” are closely related to the concept of “skill”. Consequently, the use of the term “skill” in relation to an individual implies his readiness to perform labour functions. Qualifications determine the professional qualities of a specialist that meet the production requirements. Therefore, a professionally competent professional must meet these qualification requirements [9].

DISCUSSION

Based on the above, it is necessary to ensure the high quality of education and the preparation of cadres who meet the requirements of the ongoing economic and social reforms in the country and the establishment of a prosperous democratic state. As education based on an active approach in the general secondary education system does not meet today's requirements, state educational standards based on a competency-based approach as a fundamentally new methodology of teaching general education require the development and implementation of teaching materials.

According to international pedagogical experience, it is necessary to develop the intellectual culture and professional culture of students in vocational education institutions on the basis of a competent approach. Special attention is paid to scientific research on improving the quality and effectiveness of education and the promotion of innovative approaches and technology-based professional activities in education, the development of personal and professional qualities, philosophical and professional views, and professional culture. The development of theoretical and practical bases of these directions, the definition of its psychological and pedagogical factors and conditions, content and structure, and the need to train fully mature, highly professional professionals in the period of social renewal and spiritual growth [8].

The competency approach, by its very nature, represents an effort to address a number of problems that exist in the educational process but have not yet been resolved using innovative technologies that are important for the theory and practice of education. In this regard, the competency approach incorporates the innovative processes taking place in education. This approach is directly related to the renewal of the content of education in accordance with the general concept of the educational standard of many developed countries, the transition to a system of competent approach to quality control.

This approach focuses not on the educational process, but on its outcome, the changing role of the teacher in education, and thus the change in the methods of organizing education and evaluating its outcome. In addition, a competency-based approach implies strengthening the practical orientation of education. Given the importance of existing knowledge, more emphasis is placed on its practical application.

The results of the comparative analysis show that the competency approach is more appropriate to market conditions. In addition to the formation of professional knowledge, skills and competencies based on the results of comparative analysis, the acquisition of high, specialized and innovative technologies, the development of general professional training and skills of future professionals based on the requirements of a modern market economy. The introduction of a competency-based approach also implies the educational and developmental

tasks of education, its spiritual and moral development in the process of educating the future specialist, high psychological stability and readiness for socially useful work.

Training of qualified and competitive personnel for the labour market remains a requirement of the time, increasing the competence of graduates of educational institutions.

As a result of the research, it was concluded that the professional qualities of a competent specialist should be reflected in the professional culture of students of academic lyceums, secondary special and vocational education institutions.

CONCLUSION

Given the urgency of this problem, it is necessary to study the problem of developing the professional culture of students of academic lyceums, secondary special and vocational education institutions on the basis of a competent approach from a scientific and pedagogical point of view. Developing methods to introduce a competency-based approach in the continuous development of components of students' professional culture can be a solution to the problem. This process, in turn, serves to identify the influencing psychological, pedagogical, didactic and social factors, to improve the criteria for assessing the development of professional culture.

REFERENCES

1. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2019 йил 29 апрелдаги “Ўзбекистон Республикаси халқ таълими тизимини 2030 йилгача ривожлантириш концепциясини тасдиқлаш тўғрисида” ПФ-5712-сон Фармони .
2. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2019 йил 6 сентябрдаги “Профессионал таълим тизимини янада такомиллаштиришга доир кўшимча чора-тадбирлар тўғрисида”ги ПФ-5812-сон Фармони.
3. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2020 йил 6 ноябрдаги «Ўзбекистоннинг янги тараққиёт даврида таълим-тарбия ва илм-фан соҳаларини ривожлантириш чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида»ги ПФ-6108-сон Фармони.
4. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2020 йил 6 ноябрдаги ПҚ-4884-сон “Таълим-тарбия тизимини янада такомиллаштиришга оид кўшимча чора-тадбирлар тўғрисида”ги Қарори.
5. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2020 йил 3 декабрдаги “Иқтидорли ёшларни саралаб олиш тизими ва академик лицейлар фаолиятини такомиллаштириш чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида” ПҚ-4910-сон Қарори.
6. Ниёзов Қ.А. Компетенциявий ёндашувга асосланган таълим жараёнида генетикадан масала ва машқларни ўзига хос усуллар ёрдамида ечиш методикаси. *Замонавий таълим*, 2017 й, 12-сон. 71-77-б.
7. Қодиров М.Қ., Хушвақтов Х.А., Вохидов Э.Р., Қаюмов А.О. Умумтаълим мактаблари, академик лицей ва олий таълим муассасаларида физика фанини ўқитиш сифати ва самарадорлигини ошириш масалалари. “Иқтисодиёт тармоқлари ва ижтимоий соҳанинг энергия самарадорлигини оширишга қаратилган автоматлаштириш ва энергетика муаммоларни ечишда илғор инновацион технологиялар ва таълимни ўрни” мавзусида халқаро илмий-амалий конференция материаллари. Наманган муҳандислик-технологиялар институти, 2021 йил 24-25 июнь, Наманган. 213-218 б.

8. Вахобов М.М. Компетенциявий ёндашувга асосланган давлат таълим стандартларини жорий этиш – замонавий таълим парадигмаси сифатида. *Замонавий таълим*, 2016 й, 10-сон. 3-10-б.
9. Имомов М. Профессионал таълим муассасалари ўқувчиларининг касбий маданиятини компетенциявий ёндашув асосида ривожлантириш методикасини такомиллаштириш. Пед. фан. бўйича PhD. дисс. – Т.: Педагогик инновациялар, касб-ҳунар таълими бошқарув ҳамда педагог кадрларини қайта тайёрлаш ва уларнинг малакасини ошириш институти, 2021. – 156 б.